

Chapter Two

Promises and Concerns of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Elementary Language Education: A Decade of Global Perspectives

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Abstract

In the rapidly evolving field of educational technology, the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has recently gained significant research interest, particularly in language education. This study investigates the current state of AI integration in K-6 language education by synthesizing literature from the past decade (2013-2023), indexed in Scopus and other reputable databases. By strictly following the PRISMA model, the research analyzes perspectives on the promises and concerns associated with the use of AI in elementary language education. The findings reveal a notable imbalance in research distribution and a range of optimistic and cautious viewpoints, which indicate the need for a deeper understanding of AI's role in early language education. The study identifies research gaps and provides recommendations for future research, aiming at offering valuable insights for researchers and education practitioners.

Introduction

AI is rapidly transforming various sectors, and education is no exception. The integration of AI in elementary education represents a significant shift in how foundational skills are taught, learned, and managed. This article is part of a broader research initiative exploring the multifaceted applications of AI in elementary education, including all aspects of teaching, learning, and administration. Hence, the focus zeroes in on research perspectives on the use of AI in elementary language education and how such technologies support human efforts to provide effective learning experiences.

Simulating human performance in evaluation, reasoning, decision-making, and self-development/learning has been one of the main characteristics of AI technologies (Pokrivcakova, 2019). The available literature on AI in education has exponentially grown to cover many aspects of teaching, learning, and evaluation (Chen et al., 2021), with AI being applied in profiling, prediction, analytics, adaptive systems, and intelligent tutoring and educational systems (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). Although AI's role in language learning is promising, it is still in the early development stages (Oliva et al., 2021; Yang & Kyun, 2022), which is why research is hypothetically still limited despite growing interest in research in recent years. Research has explored AI's support for specific language skills, learning strategies, intelligent digital tools, and web-based learning (Huang et al., 2023). However, a clear understanding of the potential and risks of AI in various aspects of elementary language education remains under-researched (Zhai & Wibowo, 2023).

This work discusses the analysis of perspectives on the effectiveness of AI in early language education from the last decade in terms of trending topics and research gaps to guide future research. As part of a pioneering effort to systematically review research on AI in elementary education, the focus of this paper is to address the topic by providing a comprehensive analysis of different perspectives about the integration and utilization of AI technologies. For this purpose, an overview of related work is deemed necessary for contextualizing current findings, identifying gaps, and building on the foundational knowledge of previous research.

Review of Related Work

AI in Language Education

The integration of AI in language education has gained significant attention recently. Many research studies have provided insight into the status of AI research in language education in secondary, higher or general education. Key areas of exploration include AI applications in reading, writing, vocabulary acquisition, and speaking skills (Kufel et al., 2023; Liang et al., 2023; Manire et al., 2023). Research efforts have also debated the effectiveness of AI technologies for language instruction and proficiency/competency in language development. Researchers have generally suggested a positive impact on language learning outcomes using empirical evidence (Sharadgah & Sa'di, 2022; Manire et al., 2023) in advocacy for the integration of AI to enhance educational experiences.

Various methods of AI-based language learning applications have been explored, including intelligent tutoring systems (ITS), natural language processing (NLP), and speech recognition technologies (Manire et al., 2023). Such innovative tools demonstrate how AI can enhance language learning experiences and educational outcomes. Beyond utility, the discourse on AI in language education critically challenges its ethical implications, concerns of data privacy, and the need for further pedagogical research that provides insights for safe and effective strategies to achieve pedagogical goals at any level of education (Yang & Kyun, 2022; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). Hence, it is crucial to adopt a comprehensive approach that acknowledges both the potential benefits and challenges associated with integrating AI into language education.

Perspectives and Controversies of Using AI in Language Education

The debate surrounding the integration of AI in language revolves around a range of arguments for and against its implementation. Advocates emphasize its ability to transform language learning with personalized educational experiences that are designed to cater for individual student needs and preferences (Sharadgah & Sa'di, 2022; Chen et al., 2021). AI-driven tools are perceived to make language learning more accessible, particularly for marginalized or underrepresented communities that need more inclusivity within educational settings (Manire et al., 2023). Empirical evidence suggests that AI-based language learning tools can, arguably, enhance learning outcomes by improving the outcomes of learning and pronunciation proficiency among learners. However, despite evidence for the potential benefits of AI in language learning, there is still a need for more research as the investigated aspects of language education in terms of AI use are still limited and focus on specific aspects of language learning.

Hence, criticism arises to caution the academic and education communities about the uncalculated risks of using AI and to advocate for setting the grounds for safe and scientifically founded measures to harness any potential benefits. Some critics raise concerns regarding the absence of human interaction inherent in AI-driven learning environments, emphasizing that such interactions are indispensable for fostering effective language acquisition (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). Ethical considerations also loom large with social and legal concerns surrounding data privacy and the potential for AI algorithms to perpetuate biases in language instruction (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). Critics also contend that the scope of AI may be inherently limited in addressing the multifaceted nature of language learning, more particularly in cultivating critical thinking skills and fostering cultural understanding, which needs nuanced human observations, interactions, and contextualized learning experiences (Yang & Kyun, 2022). The debate remains complex and ongoing, calling for further evidence and diverse perspectives to more fully explore the nuanced benefits and potential

drawbacks of integrating AI technologies into language education. What characterizes most of the available literature on AI in language education is the fact that it is mostly concerned with AI applications in language education at secondary/high school and tertiary levels. At the elementary level, it is hypothesized that the integration of AI in language education would show relatively similar trends and challenges as seen in secondary and higher education. This hypothesis drives the rationale for exploring research from the past decade using a robust systematic review method.

Methodology

This study is part of a bigger project that investigates the use of AI in kindergarten and elementary education. It focuses on the usage of AI in K-6 language education research between 2013 and 2023. Guided by Page et al.'s (2021) PRISMA framework for identification, screening, and inclusion, the review systematically targeted peer-reviewed literature across selected databases, namely JSTOR, ScienceDirect, ERIC, Taylor & Francis Online, and Scopus, chosen for their scholarly reputation and the quality of their published research (see Figure 2.1). A range of search terms and strategies was used to ensure covering all relevant information and identification of relevant papers by using the functionalities of each database. For screening and inter-rater reliability, we independently screened the titles and abstracts and then proceeded to full-text screening of eligibility. Discrepancies were excluded by consensus. Using Cohen's kappa (Cohen, 1960), a κ value of 0.751 was obtained, indicating high agreement. Inclusion criteria strictly required the papers to be peer-reviewed, indexed in one of the five selected databases, published in English, and focused on the use of AI in elementary language education. To be included in the analysis, papers must explicitly articulate "artificial intelligence (AI)" and "elementary/primary/early" (or an aspect of) "language education". A quality checklist was also used to evaluate the studies' validity using a quality checklist adapted from previous reviews (Sanusi et al., 2023), employing a Likert scale with scores from 0 to 10.

After the inclusion/exclusion process, data were thematically categorized into areas identified from the literature during regular meetings. The thematic analysis guiding this review was the following research questions:

RQ 01: What are the global perspectives and findings from research conducted in the past decade on the applications of AI in language and literacy education for K-6 students?

RQ 02: What recommendations for future research can be made to address the key challenges and ethical considerations of integrating AI in K-6 language education?

Figure 2.1: PRISMA flow diagram of the study selection process

Findings and Discussion

Twelve of the included papers (50%) were published between 2022 and 2023, which indicates a surge of interest in investigating the use of AI in elementary education. China contributed the most papers (n = 7), accounting for 29.17% of the total 24 papers. The United States ranked second, contributing four papers (16.67%). Several countries contributed two papers each - Australia, Korea, the Netherlands, and Taiwan - each making up 8.33% of the total. The remaining countries - Finland, Palestine, Portugal, Singapore, Spain, and the UAE - each contributed one paper, accounting for 4.17% of the total. This distribution underscores the global scope of research, reflecting contributions from a diverse range of countries. However, the fact that research is currently led by China and the USA suggests that more can be done to encourage participation and contributions from an even wider

range of nations to further advance research on AI in elementary language education. This area of research is currently in its infancy and more thematic knowledge is needed to enrich the discussion in the academic community.

The thematic analysis categorized the themes into language education themes, which include language learning/acquisition and literacy development, as well as AI themes, which include Natural Language Processing (NLP), Speech Recognition (SR), Machine Learning (ML), Generative AI, social robots, and chatbots for language education. Table 1 details the thematic breakdown for the language skills and AI technology categories. For discussion, the most prominent themes at the intersection of AI and early language education are examined, and an overview of the AI technologies and their applications in language education, as explored in the reviewed studies, is presented in Appendix 2.1.

The examination of AI integration in elementary language education reveals a clear emphasis on speaking and literacy skills and the use of dialogue systems and natural language processing technologies (see Table 2.1). This focus indicates the current educational priorities of enhancing fundamental language skills and taking advantage of interactive AI tools to engage students in meaningful, real-time conversations. The dominance of these themes suggests a recognition of their crucial role in fostering comprehensive language proficiency and creating dynamic learning environments.

Language learning/acquisition and literacy development

Several studies assert that AI integration in early language instruction impacts outcomes of learning first (L1), second (L2), and foreign languages (FL). AI-based robots, social robots, humanoids, and AI agents are used more often as tools. Social robots learn to behave like humans in their teaching methods, which have been proven to enhance L1 and L2 vocabulary and pronunciation skills (Alemi et al., 2015; Siebert et al., 2019). AI agents facilitate the process of L2 acquisition because of speech recognition and natural language processing abilities these agents possess. The use of AI-driven platforms like Google Assistant have also garnered attention for their educational benefits, particularly in enhancing speaking skills among elementary school students (Neumann et al., 2023; Smakman et al., 2021). Although speaking and listening are generally considered interrelated and interdependent skills, the research has put little emphasis and focus on the application of AI to improve the latter. That said, it is important to recognize that instructional approaches should be tailored to align with the specific affordances of AI technologies, as students engage with and respond to them in diverse ways (Wang et al., 2023b).

Table 2.1: Thematic Categories of AI Integration in Elementary Language Education (from highest to lowest frequency)

Themes	No. of Papers	Percentage
Category 1: Language Skills		
Reading/Writing/Literacy Skills	11	45.80%
Speaking	11	45.80%
Second/Foreign Language	9	37.50%
Vocabulary Acquisition	6	25%
General Language Learning	2	8.30%
Listening	1	4.20%
Sign Language	1	4.20%
Category 2: AI Technology		
Dialogue Systems/ Conversational Language Learning Chatbots	15	62.50%
Natural Language Processing	12	50%
Social Robots/Humanoids	8	33.30%
Speech/Gesture Recognition	5	20.80%
Language Generation Models	4	16.70%
Adaptive Learning Systems	3	12.50%
Artificial Neural Networks	1	4.20%
Diagnosis/Assessment Tools	1	4.20%
Eye-Tracking & Biometric Feedback	1	4.20%

On the other hand, the least addressed themes, such as sign language, listening skills, diagnostic tools, and biometric feedback technologies, indicate significant research gaps. The underrepresentation of sign language and listening skills is particularly concerning, given the importance of inclusivity and the holistic development of language competencies as well as accessibility. Limited exploration of diagnostic tools and biometric feedback technologies suggests missed opportunities for personalized and adaptive learning approaches. Addressing these gaps is critical for advancing AI’s potential and developing a more comprehensive understanding of the promises and risks of using AI to cater to diverse learner needs.

To improve speaking and pronunciation skills, social robots emerge to act as teachers, peers, or novices in their interaction with children. According to Siebert et al. (2019), anthropomorphized robots are efficient for Robot-Assisted Language Learning (RALL), which Zeng-Wei Hong and colleagues (2016) argue to be effective, as it enhances the learning outcomes and motivational levels of elementary school students. RALL involves teaching native or non-native language skills, including sign language, with the use of robots (Randall, 2020). The integration of AI in early language education offers promising opportunities for enhancing language learning across various contexts. Social robots and AI agents can provide personalized, engaging, and interactive learning experiences, improving linguistic proficiency and communicative competence. A key area where AI innovation could significantly impact is literacy.

Literacy development

Although literacy can be considered part of language learning, the fact that it is explicitly explored in connection to AI research makes it a central theme on its own. The importance of early literacy has urged many researchers to experiment with AI and identify the benefits of reading robots and AI-enhanced chatbots in offering children literacy and emotional awareness activities interactively. Chatbots serve as reading companions that help sustain learners' interest in reading, thereby supporting ongoing engagement and improving reading comprehension (Michaelis & Mutlu, 2018). Literature offers ways through which literacy can be innovatively improved for early learners (Bueno-Rocha et al., 2023; Jauhainen & Guerra, 2023; Liu et al., 2022; Zhang & Liu, 2024). Generative AI affords personalized assistive reading and writing for early learners in the sense that teachers can have access to AI-generated text that responds to different literacy needs. AI tools, like Carolina Automated Reading Evaluation (CARE), automate screening for reading difficulties, allowing for timely interventions. AI also tends to support low-literacy children and those with disabilities; systems such as SiLearn help the deaf acquire vocabulary, and developments in image recognition generate braille materials for blind students. Each of these technologies allows educators to advance literacy ability on the pathway to success in school and lifelong learning, heeding the diverse learning needs of students. AI-enhanced literacy application is still in its infancy, and more research is needed to find better ways and identify best practices and AI technologies to assist learners with learning challenges. More importantly, there is a need for a better understanding of how AI exactly improves literacy, part of which is discussed below, and how different factors correlate with different aspects of language literacy.

Artificial Intelligence Technologies: NLP, SR, ML, GenAI, Social Robots, Generative AI.

Relatively similar to AI applications in language education in secondary/high schools and tertiary education (see Literature Review), the most common AI technologies used and explored by researchers in the last decade tend to focus on human language processing, machine learning, content generation, social robots, and chatbots for language teaching and learning. This is indicative of the importance of such technologies in developing tools that can provide better teaching methodologies for the teachers and better language learning experiences for the learners.

Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Speech Recognition (SR)

Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Speech Recognition (SR) have been discussed in terms of their capabilities to imitate human behavior to communicate with children in a "human-to-human" manner. The language learning process utilizes several techniques of NLP and SR; for example, a baby reading robot that applies NLP to recognize emotions and realize voice interaction, thus improving educational communication (Zhang & Liu, 2024). NLP and SR technologies enable AI agents to individualize instruction and communicate with students through interactive interfaces. NLP is also used by chatbots (see *Social Robots and Chatbots for Language Education* below) to extract information from texts and generate responses that answer the needs/questions of the users. Yet, it remains challenging to develop effective chatbots for high-level learners (Chang et al., 2023; Yin & Muge, 2020) because research generally focuses on low achievers or struggling learners more than other categories of learning profiles. Though Siebert and colleagues (2019) express their concerns regarding the accessibility of SR for all children in the sense that it implies possible inequalities for children with special needs, NLP and SR technologies are potential drivers of innovation in early language education, supporting personalization and inclusivity in learning environments. The more these technologies are developed, the better their capabilities are used for innovation. Research on

innovative ways to enhance SR to support children with speech and language deficits is important to serve this group of children.

Machine Learning and Generative AI

Machine Learning (ML) and Generative AI (GenAI) enhance learning experiences by enabling more interactive and personalized educational support. ML techniques allow robots to comprehend book content and engage in interactive learning with elementary students, while GenAI tools, such as ChatGPT and Deepseek, facilitate the development of reading, vocabulary, and writing skills by generating contextually appropriate language and providing immediate, adaptive responses (Liu et al., 2022; Jauhiainen & Guerra, 2023). This relieves some burden off teachers and helps them focus more on the learner rather than the learning materials (Luo et al., 2024). The cons of this change, however, would be accessibility and accountability for young children. ML and GenAI can provide personalized learning and amplify the teacher's ability to cater to a wide range of learning needs, but they require proper consideration of ethical implications. Due to the novelty of these tools, teachers need training and guidance with policies, culturally informed guidelines, and AI skills (such as prompt engineering) to maximize the potential of AI in resource supply that caters to specific students' academic needs in their cultural contexts.

Social Robots and Chatbots for Language Education

Social robots are found to be valuable in elementary language teaching because they provide interaction and engagement; they can play an important role in teaching languages (Aleml et al., 2015; Smakman et al., 2021). For example, social assistive robotics, such as iRobi, could perform storytelling and interactive games (Fridin, 2014). In addition, baby reading robots that recognize emotions have been introduced and found to foster communication skills in a supporting learning environment (Zhang & Liu, 2024). It can be argued that social robots are expected to play a supportive role in future classrooms. Rather than relying on a single teacher to manage all instructional tasks, robots may assume responsibilities that allow for individualized interaction and attention, thereby enabling teachers to focus on more complex aspects of instruction and the provision of emotional support. This complementary collaboration between teachers and AI-driven robots has the potential to enhance student engagement and make learning experiences more effective and stimulating.

AI chatbots provide individualized, interactive language learning opportunities for students. Speaking skills might be better enhanced through voice-based chatbots, which can also maintain interest in reading with the aid of book talks and storybook reading (Chang et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2022. Xu et al., 2021, 2022). Jeon (2023) and Wang et al. (2023b) describe the pedagogical, technological, and social benefits of AI chatbots to foster a stress-free learning environment both for teachers and their respective students. By applying the potential offered by generative AI, these social robots and AI-powered chatbots provide students with highly engaging and supportive learning experiences, individually tailored to the development of proficient language use and to enhance learner engagement. However, technical challenges remain, particularly in addressing pronunciation variations among kindergarten and early-grade learners who are still developing foundational speaking skills. Current research has not adequately examined the specific conditions under which these challenges arise. Further investigation is needed to better understand and optimize the role of AI chatbots in supporting early language development.

Challenges and Future Research Recommendations

Relatively similar to higher phases of language education, the discourse hinging around the integration of AI in elementary language education encapsulates a spectrum of arguments both in

favor of and against its adoption and utilization. Advocates of AI highlight its potential to revolutionize language learning through personalized learning experiences that take into consideration the needs of individual students and their preferences (Abdullah Sharadgah & Abdulatif Sa'di, 2022; Chen et al., 2021). AI-driven methodologies are promoted for their potential to enhance accessibility in language learning, especially for marginalized or underrepresented communities that need more inclusivity in educational settings. Research indicates that AI-based language learning tools can improve learning outcomes and pronunciation proficiency in elementary school (Manire et al., 2023). However, and counter to such confidence, there is a recognized need for further empirical research to explore specific aspects of language learning impacted by AI integration at the elementary phase.

Critics also caution against uncalculated risks of AI integration in education and advocate instead for scientifically grounded measures to maximize benefits and minimize risks. Concerns include the absence of human interaction in AI-driven learning environments, which is argued to be crucial for effective language acquisition. Ethical considerations such as data privacy and the potential for AI algorithms to perpetuate biases also loom large (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). Furthermore, AI may be limited in its ability to foster critical thinking, cultural understanding and other aspects of learning that benefit from nuanced human interactions and contextualized experiences (Yang & Kyun, 2022). The debate continues about the benefits and risks of AI, and the need for comprehensive exploration of both its advantages and limitations in elementary language education should be taken into account for further research.

There are several areas that have been found to need further exploration to better evaluate the potential that using AI may have on language education. Notable is the fact that research has not extensively been carried out on some critical aspects of language, including grammar and listening comprehension (Neumann et al., 2023; Smakman et al., 2021). Although literacy and reading skills, as noted earlier, have been explored extensively, other components necessary for the effective development of all the pillars of language have not been adequately explored. Hence, more research is required to document the long-term effects of integrating AI on elementary student language development and general academic achievement. Although not yet of significant importance since the research is still in its infancy stage regarding this topic, another gap identified is the limited geographical distribution in research studies, with both China and the USA leading most of these studies so far. Expanding geographical scope is important in creating inclusive findings that can be used across diverse educational setups globally, especially regarding policymaking that requires diverse global perspectives.

As the use of AI in education increases, policy development towards the assurance of ethics and safety should be emphasized. Policymakers should set policies on how different groups of students shall have access to AI tools so that one group does not disadvantage the other due to a lack of resources. Some of the concerns that the ethical framework should address include data privacy, consent, and not over-relying on AI at the cost of human interaction. Serious ethical issues in the use of AI technologies are related to accessibility and equity, especially for marginalized communities and in developing education systems. There is a pressing need for policymakers to establish comprehensive guidelines that ensure equitable access to AI tools for all students, including those with special educational needs and those from under-resourced communities (Siebert et al., 2019). This access should not compromise the privacy and security of children's data. This area of concern has not been adequately explored and not sufficiently discussed in the academic community; hence, more efforts are needed for better assessment of the risk and development of necessary policies. In these policies, the psychological effects of AI on children should also be considered so that its use in a classroom enhances and provides the best and most appropriate learning experiences for children without creating a dependency or minimizing the human interaction deemed essential in early childhood. Such

policies help various education stakeholders to design safe and equitable frameworks for the implementation of AI in early language education.

More research is also needed to close these gaps and further refine the use of AI in early language education. By studying additional, relatively less-understood language skills and diverse geographies, future research will increase the generalizability of research findings. Further, there should be more research on the development and testing of novel AI applications and methodologies. Longitudinal studies may also be warranted to investigate the long-term benefits and potential drawbacks of AI in elementary education. Ethical considerations in AI research and framework development shall ensure that its integration supports equitable and effective language learning outcomes (Akgun & Greenhow, 2022). Strengthening these research areas can assist the education community in maximizing the transformational potential of AI and, therefore, supporting more inclusive and effective learning environments for young learners.

Future research should also explore opportunities for extending the applications of AI in elementary language education to new areas and those that have been underexplored, such as sign language, grammar, and listening comprehension. Longitudinal studies should be used to understand the long-term effects of AI integration on language learning and to identify best practices in sustainable implementation. Studies should also look at the effectiveness of the different models of AI-human interaction in the classroom to establish the trade-off that is optimal in enhancing learning while at the same time capturing what is essentially human.

Researchers can further explore the pedagogical frameworks that best support the use of AI in language learning at different levels of education (elementary vs middle vs secondary vs higher education). This includes investigating how AI technologies may effectively be infused into established curricula and teaching practices to supplement tradition-driven instructional methods. Studies should be conducted to determine the right balance between AI-driven and human-driven instruction to gain the best learning outcome for students. In the same vein, studies should focus on developing adaptive learning systems in which educational content is adapted to individual students, thus achieving differentiated instruction for diverse learning profiles. Educators, AI developers, and researchers will have to work together to create such platforms. Future research should bridge these gaps and further the knowledge of the role of AI in education in general for the improved effective, inclusive, and ethical use of AI in earlier language learning.

Conclusion

This review examined the current state of research on integrating AI into elementary language education (K-6). An analysis of studies published between 2013 and 2023 revealed a significant increase in academic research interest, with speaking and literacy (including reading) skills dominating topics of interest in L1, L2, and FL learning. Although research is still in its infancy and too early to generalize findings, AI-powered tools—such as social robots and chatbots—have been reported to provide personalized learning experiences; NLP and SR technologies are leading for interactive and individualized instruction. However, there are still major gaps in the research: under-researched issues like listening and grammar, ethical concerns around data privacy, accessibility, and possible bias which could be addressed by policymaking efforts at a global level.

With only 24 studies available for the analysis, the research scope is geographically limited as well, with most studies being led by China and the USA, so broader research is needed to establish the generalizability of the findings across different educational contexts. Further studies need to investigate relatively under-researched areas such as sign language and listening comprehension, focusing on their longitudinal dimensions to establish the long-term effects of AI on language

learning. The purpose of research should be to explore and refine pedagogical frameworks that outline best practices in achieving maximum balance between AI-driven and human-driven instruction within the classroom environment. Addressing these research gaps through sustained collaboration among key stakeholders, including educators, AI developers, and researchers, is critical to unlocking the full potential of AI in elementary language education. Such collaborative efforts can contribute to the creation of a more inclusive, effective, and ethically responsible learning environment for young learners.

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Appendix 2.1

Overview of AI Technologies and Language Education Applications in Selected Studies

Study	AI Technology	Language Education
Bueno et al. (2023)	Dialogue Systems/ Conversational/Language Learning Chatbots Natural Language Processing Language Generation Models	Speaking Reading/Writing/Literacy Skills
Chang et al. (2023)	Speech/Gesture Recognition Natural Language Processing Language Generation Models	Vocabulary Acquisition
Fridin (2014)	Dialogue Systems/ Conversational/ Language Learning Chatbots Social Robots/Humanoids	Speaking
Zeng-Wei Hong et al. (2016)	Dialogue Systems/ Conversational/Language Learning Chatbots/ Social Robots/Humanoids	Speaking L2 and FL
Hoskins et al. (2021)	Diagnosis Tools Eye-Tracking & Biometric Feedback	Speaking Reading/Writing/Literacy Skills
Jauhainen and Garagorry (2023)	Dialogue Systems/ Conversational/Language Learning Chatbots /Natural Language Processing Language Generation Models	Reading/Writing/Literacy Skills Vocabulary Acquisition
Jeon (2023)	Natural Language Processing Dialogue Systems/ Conversational/Language Learning Chatbots/	Reading/Writing/Literacy Skills Vocabulary Acquisition
Martínez-Ramón and Gil (2023)	Artificial Neural Networks	Reading/Writing/Literacy Skills
Liu et al. (2022)	Dialogue Systems Conversational/Language Learning Bots and Chatbots	Reading/Writing/Literacy Skills L2 and FL
Liu and Lu (2023)	Speech/Gesture Recognition Natural Language Processing	Speaking Foreign Language Education
Luo et al. (2024)	Dialogue Systems/ Conversational/Language Learning Chatbots/Language Generation Models	General Language Learning
Neumann (2020)	Social Robots/Humanoids	General Language Learning Reading/Writing/Literacy Skills L2 and FL
Neumann et al. (2023)	Dialogue Systems/ Conversational/Language Learning Chatbots/ Social Robots/Humanoids	Speaking Reading/Writing/Literacy Skills L2 and FL
Sandberg et al. (2014)	Social Robots/Humanoids Adaptive Learning Systems	Reading/Writing/Literacy Skills Vocabulary Acquisition L2 and FL
Siebert et al. (2019)	Dialogue Systems/ Conversational/Language Learning Chatbots/Social Robots/Humanoids Speech/Gesture Recognition Natural Language Processing	Speaking Vocabulary Acquisition
Smakman et al. (2021)	Dialogue Systems/ Conversational/Language Learning Chatbots/Social Robots/Humanoids	L2 and FL Sign language Speaking and listening skills
So and Lee (2023)	Dialogue Systems/ Conversational/Language Learning Chatbots Social Robots/Humanoids	L2 and FL

	Natural Language Processing	
Wang et al. (2023a)	Dialogue Systems/ Conversational/Language Learning Chatbots/Natural Language Processing Adaptive Learning Systems Diagnosis/Assessment Tools	Reading/Writing/Literacy Skills, L2 and FL
Wang et al. (2023b)	Dialogue Systems/ Conversational/Language Learning Chatbots/Natural Language Processing	Speaking Reading/Writing/Literacy Skills L2 and FL
Wu and Yu (2023)	Natural Language Processing	Speaking Reading/Writing/Literacy Skills
Xu et al. (2021)	Reading/Writing/Literacy Skills	Dialogue Systems/ Conversational/Language Learning Chatbots/Adaptive Learning Systems
Xu et al. (2022)	Dialogue Systems/ Conversational/Language Learning Chatbots/Speech/Gesture Recognition Natural Language Processing	Speaking Reading/Writing/Literacy Skills
Zhang and Liu and (2024)	Speech/Gesture Recognition, Natural Language Processing	Reading/Writing/Literacy Skills